

ASSOCIATION OF AGE WITH GLEASON GRADE IN PATIENTS OF LOCALIZED PROSTATE CANCER

Dr. Syed Saif Ul Hassan Shah^{*1}, Dr Muhammad Nadeem², Dr. Faisal Mahmood³, Dr. Irfan Ali⁴, Dr. Muhammad Sajid Hussain⁵, Dr. Muhammad Umair⁶

^{*1,4,5}Consultant Medical Specialist CMH RWP

^{2,3}Consultant medical Oncologist CMH RWP

⁶Consultant medical Oncologist PNS SHIFA

¹saima_kazmi57@hotmail.com, ²dr_nadeempiracha@hotmail.com, ³drfaisalmehmood@yahoo.com, ⁴irfansoomro19@yahoo.com, ⁵sajidrao88@gmail.com, ⁶drumair391@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15314556>

Keywords

Age; Gleason grade; PSA; Prostate cancer

Article History

Received on 22 March 2025
Accepted on 22 April 2025
Published on 30 April 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Dr. Syed Saif Ul Hassan
Shah

Abstract

OBJECTIVE: To look for association of age and other clinical factors with Gleason grade in patients of localized prostate cancer

STUDY DESIGN: Cross-sectional Study

SETTING AND DURATION: Medical Oncology Department, Combined Military Hospital Rawalpindi (CMH). December 2021 to December 2023

METHODOLOGY: This study was conducted on 140 male patients of newly diagnosed localized prostate cancer. All the patients underwent biopsy of prostate by standard protocol which was assessed by a consultant histopathologist. Gleason score as well as Gleason grade was assigned by the pathologist on the report. Age of the patient was ascertained by checking from national identity card. Clinical parameters other than age were recorded from clinical charts of the patients.

RESULTS: A total of 140 male patients with localized prostate cancer were recruited for this analysis. Mean age of the patients we included in this study was 66.27±6.08 years. Out of total patients studied, 58 (41.4%) had Gleason Grade-I, 16 (11.4%) had Gleason grade-II, 29 (20.7%) had Gleason grade-III, 17 (12.1%) had Gleason grade-IV while 20 (14.3%) patients had Gleason Grade-V. Statistical analysis revealed that advancing age had statistically significant association with high Gleason grade in our study participants (p-value<0.001).

CONCLUSION: Patients of prostate cancer included in our study had Gleason grades I to V. Increasing age was found to be associated with high Gleason grade in patients of localized prostate cancer recruited in this study.

INTRODUCTION

Cancers have high mortality and morbidity despite a lot of advancements in treatment options.¹ Prostate cancer is one of the most commonly encountered neoplastic condition among males especially elderly males.² Depending upon extent of prostatic tissue or other parts involved it may be classified as localized,

advanced or metastatic cancer.³ Pathologist in most of the cases not only diagnose the cancer but also comment on Gleason score and grade of cancer which is directly linked to prognosis and treatment response. Gleason scoring is calculated by histopathologist by analyzing the sample from two different locations and

comparing the cancer cells with normal cells,⁴ and then on the basis of Gleason score calculate Gleason grade. Higher the Gleason grade; worse is the prognosis in most of the cases.⁵ There could be multiple socio-demographic and clinical factors which could affect the Gleason score and grade and eventually prognosis and overall response of the disease to treatment.⁶

Age of the patient can impact the disease process in number of ways and should be taken into account at the time of diagnosis and management. Abudoubari et al. in 2023 analyzed various epidemiological factors associated with prognosis in patients suffering from prostate cancer and found age as an important factor determining the prognosis of patients suffering from this neoplastic condition.⁷ Zhou et al. in 2022 studied around 374 men suffering from prostate cancer and tried to look for the difference in pattern of cancer in elderly adults and compared to younger adults. They could not generate any convincing evidence about this phenomenon.⁸ Shah et al. published a study from USA and tried to establish relationship between age and Gleason grade among patients suffering from prostate cancer. They came up with the conclusion that these two variables had significant association and elderly males had more chances of having high Gleason grade as compared to younger males.¹⁰ Cancer of prostate gland is commonly managed in urology and oncology clinics in various tertiary care hospitals of Pakistan. A recent local study published from Karachi revealed that age had a weak association with Gleason grade among patients suffering from prostate cancer and this relationship was influenced by other clinical variables as well.¹⁰ Management plan for patients of prostatic cancer involves various modalities and tolerability of treatment is also a factor which could be influenced by advancing age. Limited local data has been available regarding relationship of age and Gleason grade in these patients. We therefore planned this study with the rationale to look for association of age and other clinical factors with Gleason grade in patients managed for localized prostate cancer.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Medical Oncology department of Combined Military hospital Rawalpindi from December 2021 to

December 2023. Sample population was gathered by using the non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Sample size was calculated by using the WHO sample size calculator by using population prevalence proportion of prostate cancer in Pakistan as 5.2%¹¹ and margin of error as 5%.

Inclusion criteria: All male patients between the age of 40 and 80 years diagnosed with localized prostate cancer were recruited for this study.

Exclusion criteria: Patients more than 80 years of age or those who refused to undergo biopsy were not recruited. Those with metastatic disease were also not made part of this study. Patients whose biopsy report was not clear or Gleason score was not mentioned by the pathologist were excluded. Those patients whose national identity card or valid document showing age were missing were not included.

Ethical approval (via letter number XXX) was taken from the ethical review board committee of Combined Military Hospital Rawalpindi. Prostate cancer was diagnosed either by consultant urologist or oncologist on the basis of histopathological findings.¹² Metastasis was ruled out by the clinical team after carrying out relevant investigations. Gleason scoring was calculated by histopathologist on the basis of cellular comparison of cancer cells with normal cell. Gleason grade was assigned to the patients on the basis of Gleason score from 1-V.¹³ Serum PSA levels and tumor size were assessed for each patient at the time of diagnosis and biopsy. Sociodemographic factors were recorded from all the patients and entered into a structured proforma. Age was the variable of interest for the researchers so extreme caution was taken while ascertaining the age and national identity card or any other valid document was used for this purpose. Levels of Prostatic Specific Antigen (PSA) were considered extremely elevated if they were more than 10 ng/dl.¹⁴ All statistical analysis was performed by using the Statistics Package for Social Sciences version 24.0 (SPSS-24.0). Mean and standard deviation was calculated for the age of patients. Frequency and percentages were calculated for Gleason grades, abnormal PSA levels, large tumor size and different age brackets. Pearson Chi-square test was applied to look for the association of various factors including age with Gleason grade of study participants. The p-

value of less than or equal to 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

A total of 140 male patients with localized prostate cancer were recruited for this analysis. Mean age of the patients we included in this study was 66.27±6.08 years. Table-I showed the summary of characteristics of patients of localized prostate cancer included in our study. Out of total patients studied, 58 (41.4%) had

Gleason Grade-I, 16 (11.4%) had Gleason grade-II, 29 (20.7%) had Gleason grade-III, 17 (12.1%) had Gleason grade-IV while 20 (14.3%) patients had Gleason Grade-V.

Table-II showed the results of data processing done by the statistical team for this study. Statistical analysis revealed that advancing age had statistically significant association with high Gleason grade in our study participants (p-value<0.001).

Table-I: Characteristics of patients with localized prostate cancer

Study parameters	n (%)
Age (years) Mean ± SD	66.27±6.08 years
Marital status	
Married	107 (76.4%)
Never married	19 (13.6%)
Divorced	05 (3.6%)
Widow	09 (6.4%)
Gleason grade	
I	58 (41.4%)
II	16 (11.4%)
III	29 (20.7%)
IV	17 (12.1%)
V	20 (14.3%)
Age Bracket	
<60 years	48 (34.3%)
60-70 years	65 (46.4%)
>70 years	27 (19.3%)
PSA levels	
Extremely elevated	63 (45%)
Not extremely elevated	77 (55%)

Table-II: Association of various factors with Gleason grade in our study participants

Factors	Grade I	Grade II	Grade III	Grade IV	Grade V	p-value
Age						
<60 years	30 (51.7%)	07 (43.7%)	06 (20.6%)	01 (5.8%)	04 (20%)	<0.001
60-70 years	25 (43.1%)	05 (31.3%)	15 (51.7%)	10 (58.8%)	10 (50%)	
>70 years	03 (5.1%)	04 (25%)	08 (27.6%)	06 (35.3%)	06 (30%)	
PSA Levels						
Not extremely elevated	30 (51.7%)	08 (50%)	15 (51.7%)	13 (76.5%)	11 (55%)	0.417
Extremely elevated	28 (48.3%)	08 (50%)	14 (48.3%)	04 (23.5%)	09 (45%)	
Tumor size						
T1 and T2	35 (60.3%)	07 (43.7%)	18 (62.1%)	11 (64.7%)	13 (65%)	0.710
T3 and T4	23 (39.7%)	09 (56.3%)	11 (37.9%)	06 (35.3%)	07 (35%)	

DISCUSSION

Any disease process in elderly could be difficult to

manage and situation becomes more difficult if disease process is neoplastic or metastatic. Multiple

risk factors may be involved in predicting prognosis of disease; few may be modifiable and sometimes disease pattern may be different with difference in sociodemography like age or gender. Many cancerous conditions follow similar pattern. Clinicians and researches have similar idea regarding prostate cancer that with age, the behavior and pattern of cancer may be completely different. We tried to work on this and conducted this study with an aim to look for association of age and other clinical factors with Gleason grade in patients managed for localized prostate cancer at our hospital.

Taggart et al. in 2023 analysed upstaging of Gleason 3+3 prostate cancer and found out that higher Gleason grade transformation predicted poor outcome and more the age of the patient; more were the chances of upstaging in Gleason grade.¹⁵We did not study the response to treatment but analysed the relationship between age and Gleason grade at the time of diagnosis of localized prostate cancer and found out that advancing age was associated with higher Gleason grade in our study participants.

Shah et al. studied 5100 patients of prostate cancer for their Gleason grade and found out that most of the patients who had high Gleason grade were of age more than 65 years. There was a clear trend seen in their study that higher age was associated with high Gleason grade.¹⁶ Our results supported the findings generated by Shah et al. high Gleason grade was statistically significantly associated with increasing age in our study.

Clark et al. published a study from Canada and studied data set of more than 10000 patients of prostate cancer. They studied effect of age on prostate cancer survival and found out that patients who were more aged had high Gleason grade and lesser chances of 5 and 10-year survival as compared to those who were of lesser age.¹⁷Ours was not a study type which did survival analysis but only studied relationship of age and Gleason grade and which turned out to be significant.

Wang et al. published a meta-analysis and systematic review regarding factors related to upgrading of Gleason grade in patients suffering from prostate cancer. They found out that age, prostatic volume and PSA levels were associated with high Gleason grade in data they generated from different relevant studies.¹⁸ In our set of patients, tumour size and PSA levels were

not found associated with higher Gleason grade but age was significantly associated with high Gleason grade.

Study limitations

Time lapse after start of disease till diagnosis can effect Gleason score and grade. Time of presentation and diagnosis which could not be uniform for all the study participants as in a tertiary care setup referrals are made from all the peripheral areas and local and remote patients have different time lapse from start of disease process till diagnosis.

CONCLUSION

Patients of prostate cancer included in our study had Gleason grades I to V. Increasing age was found to be associated with high Gleason grade in patients of localized prostate cancer recruited in this study.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No author has any conflict of interest

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

None

REFERENCES

- Siegel RL, Miller KD, Fuchs HE, Jemal A. Cancer Statistics, 2021. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2021 Jan;71(1):7-33. doi: 10.3322/caac.21654. Epub 2021 Jan 12. PMID: 33433946.
- Bergengren O, Pekala KR, Matsoukas K, Fainberg J, Mungovan SF, Bratt et al. 2022 Update on Prostate Cancer Epidemiology and Risk Factors-A Systematic Review. *Eur Urol.* 2023;84(2):191-206. doi:10.1016/j.eururo.2023.04.021
- Lowrance W, Dreicer R, Jarrard DF, Scarpato KR, Kim SK, Kirkby E et al. Updates to Advanced Prostate Cancer: AUA/SUO Guideline (2023). *J Urol.* 2023;209(6):1082-1090. doi:10.1097/JU.0000000000003452
- Zhou AG, Salles DC, Samarska IV, Epstein JI. How Are Gleason Scores Categorized in the Current Literature: An Analysis and Comparison of Articles Published in 2016-2017. *Eur Urol.* 2019 Jan;75(1):25-31. doi: 10.1016/j.eururo.2018.07.021. Epub 2018 Jul 26. PMID: 30057131.

- Zelic R, Giunchi F, Fridfeldt J, Carlsson J, Davidsson S, Lianas L, et al. Prognostic Utility of the Gleason Grading System Revisions and Histopathological Factors Beyond Gleason Grade. *Clin Epidemiol.* 2022 Jan 18;14(3):59-70. doi: 10.2147/CLEP.S339140. PMID: 35082531; PMCID: PMC8784949.
- Zhang B, Wu S, Zhang Y, Guo M, Liu R. Analysis of risk factors for Gleason score upgrading after radical prostatectomy in a Chinese cohort. *Cancer Med.* 2021 Nov;10(21):7772-7780. doi: 10.1002/cam4.4274. Epub 2021 Sep 16. PMID: 34528767; PMCID: PMC8559471.
- Abudoubari S, Bu K, Mei Y, Maimaitiyiming A, An H, Tao N. Prostate cancer epidemiology and prognostic factors in the United States. *Front Oncol.* 2023 Oct 12;13(3):1142976. doi: 10.3389/fonc.2023.1142976. PMID: 37901326; PMCID: PMC10603232.
- Zhou CD, Pettersson A, Plym A, Tyekucheva S, Penney KL, Sesso HD, et al. Differences in Prostate Cancer Transcriptomes by Age at Diagnosis: Are Primary Tumors from Older Men Inherently Different? *Cancer Prev Res (Phila).* 2022 Dec 1;15(12):815-825. doi: 10.1158/1940-6207.CAPR-22-0212. PMID: 36125434; PMCID: PMC9722523.
- Shah N, Ioffe V, Kapur A. A comparative analysis of prostate cancer pre-treatment characteristics stratified by age. *Can J Urol.* 2014 Apr;21(2):7213-6. PMID: 24775574.
- Abdullah A, Ali N, Malik Z. To Evaluate the Corelation between Age and Gleason Score in Patients with Prostate Cancer- A Tertiary Care Hospital Based Study. *Liaq Nation J Can Care* 2021; 3(1): 7-10.
- Akhtar S, Hassan F, Ahmad S, El-Affendi MA, Khan MI. The prevalence of prostate cancer in Pakistan: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Heliyon.* 2023 Sep 20;9(10):e20350. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e20350. PMID: 37767511; PMCID: PMC10520826.
- Descotes JL. Diagnosis of prostate cancer. *Asian J Urol.* 2019 Apr;6(2):129-136. doi: 10.1016/j.ajur.2018.11.007. Epub 2019 Feb 14. PMID: 31061798; PMCID: PMC6488713.
- Chen N, Zhou Q. The evolving Gleason grading system. *Chin J Cancer Res.* 2016 Feb;28(1):58-64. doi: 10.3978/j.issn.1000-9604.2016.02.04. PMID: 27041927; PMCID: PMC4779758.
- Atan A, Güzel Ö. How should prostate specific antigen be interpreted? *Turk J Urol.* 2013 Sep;39(3):188-93. doi: 10.5152/tud.2013.038. PMID: 26328106; PMCID: PMC4548626.
- Taggart R, Dutto L, Leung HY, Salji M, Ahmad I. A contemporary analysis of disease upstaging of Gleason 3 + 3 prostate cancer patients after robot-assisted laparoscopic prostatectomy. *Cancer Med.* 2023 Nov;12(22):20830-20837. doi: 10.1002/cam4.6651. Epub 2023 Nov 6. PMID: 37929881; PMCID: PMC10709727.
- Shah N, Ioffe V. Frequency of Gleason score 7 to 10 in 5100 elderly prostate cancer patients. *Rev Urol.* 2016;18(4):181-187. doi: 10.3909/riu0732. PMID: 28127259; PMCID: PMC5260947.
- Clark R, Vesprini D, Narod SA. The Effect of Age on Prostate Cancer Survival. *Cancers (Basel).* 2022 Aug 27;14(17):4149. doi: 10.3390/cancers14174149. PMID: 36077685; PMCID: PMC9454626.
- Wang Y, Chen X, Liu K, Liu R, Li L, Yin C, Song P. Predictive Factors for Gleason Score Upgrading in Patients with Prostate Cancer after Radical Prostatectomy: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Urol Int.* 2023;107(5):460-479. doi: 10.1159/000528873. Epub 2023 Mar 29. PMID: 36990065.